

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL MONUMENTS IN THE TERRITORY OF ANCIENT KESH REGION

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Annotation: The article covers the history and historiography of the formation and development of the city surface of ancient Kesh. The history of the study of the history of the ancient Kesh region and cities began 150 years ago, and the original location of ancient Kesh was located in the territory of the present-day Kitab district, which was discovered by the archaeological topographical expedition of Kesh organized by M.E. Masson.

Key words: Kesh, Shahrisabz, Yakkabogh, historical geography, Qairagoch village, Daratepa, Surkhondaryo, Bandikhontepa, Podayotoktepa, Defense wall, Bactria, Kiziltepa, Podayotoktepa, Uzungir and Sangirtepa.

At the end of 1870, naturalist A.L. Kun, member of Turkestan amateur archaeologists circle V.N.Litvinov, in 1916 I.A.Kastane, photographer G.E.Krivtsov and historical topographer N. The Sitniakovskys started in cooperation. In their time, they assumed that Kesh was in the city of Shahrisabz, without knowing exactly where it was located. The first orientalist to approach the history of Kesh in a scientific way is V.V. Bartold [1, p. 423-454]. In 1925, Shahrisabz was founded by Orientalist V.V. Bartold, archaeologist and local historian V.L. Vyatkin, art historians B. N. Denike and E. Kohn-Wiener studied. In 1926, A. Yu. Yakubovsky first studied the historical topography [2, p. 16-19]

From the 1930s, Ya. G'. Gulomov, T. Mirgiyozov and S. K. Kabanov began to research archaeological and memorial monuments. In the years of the Second World War, i.e. in 1942, as an inspector of UZKOMSTARIS (Uzbekstanskiy komitet po delam muzeev i okhrany pamyatnikov stariny, iskusstva i prirody) to the city of Shahrisabz, M.E. Masson and G.A. Pugachenkova, as a result of the research conducted in the Shahrisabz region, discovered the ancient Kesh region, the research of the historical geography of its central city and villages began [3, p.16]. By comparing the historical topography of Kesh with written sources, they proved that the ancient city was located on the site of Qalandartepa, instead of the city of Kitab. In 1946-1948, S.K. Kabanov conducted preliminary archaeological excavations in Kesh [4, p. 177-114].

In a sense, the study of the historical geography of Kesh is related to the activity of "Kesh Archaeological Topographic Expedition" by M.E. Masson in 1963 [5, p. 60-64]. N. I. Krasheninnikova conducted research in the Kitab-Kesh

region, Z.I.Usmanova and S.B.Lunina in the Shahrisabz-Kesh region, and G.Dresvyanskaya in the Yakkabog region. N.I. Krashennnikova's researches in Podayotoqtepa, Uzunqir, Sangirtepa, Qalandartepa located in the center of Kitab city in the Shurobsoy valley [6, p. 460].

S.Kabanov, G.Dresvyanskaya and Z.Usmanova in 1976-1985 conducted field research to create a map of archaeological monuments located in Yakkabog district and identified more than 300 archaeological monuments [7, p. 25-29]. According to the data, 20 percent of them are ancient, 70 percent belong to the early middle ages, and 30 percent belong to the developed middle ages [8. s. 25-29]. A.S. Sagdullaev researched village ruins of the VII-VI centuries BC in Daratepa, located near the village of Qairaghoch in the Yakkabog district, and noted several other archaeological monuments of the early Iron Age [9. s. 457., pp. 154-161].

The main archaeological researches were carried out by the "Kesh Archaeological Topographic Expedition" under the leadership of Academician M.E. Masson at the Tashkent State University, and S.K. Kabanov, V.D. Zhukov, G.Ya.Dresvyanskaya, Z.I.Usmanova together with the students. , A.S.Sagdullaev, N.I.Krashennnikova, N.P.Stolyarova, P.Niyazov, E.Bakhshitsyan, O.N.Lushpenkova S.B.Lunina participated. S.B. Lunina's special historical geography "Istoricheskoy geografii Yuzhnogo Sogda VIII - XII vv." monograph is also a work with valuable information [10, p. 109-127]. Academician A. Sagdullaev, one of the researchers, analyzed new archeological and written sources and found out that the building on the site of Sangirtepa functioned as an "open-air temple" in the 10th-9th centuries BC. The date of Sangir-III archeological layer belongs to the VII-VI centuries BC, during this period the expansion of the city and the growth of the population are observed. Researcher M. Khasanov identified 3 periods of construction and repair of the defensive walls at Podayotoqtepe, and found out that its architecture is similar to the Qiziltepa monument, which is part of the Bactrian state, and that it was built in 3 parts in the 7th century BC [11. b. 21].

In the sources there is information about the existence of a large temple in Kesh in the 7th century, where the soldiers of the army sacrificed thousands of sheep before military campaigns. Such a large temple can be the monument of Sangirtepa preserved in Komirtepa village of Kitab district [12. s. 65].

From the pottery found in this place as a result of archaeological excavations, there are glasses, vases, bowls, textile stones, a piece of brick, pieces of pottery with marks of the potters pouring into their products, a statue made

of a snake, iron knives and military weapons, which are a unique historical evidence of the strengthening of the city's defense capabilities. are sources.

The emergence of the first city in the place of Podayotoqtepa, Uzunqir and Sangirtepa can be connected with the process of the emergence of the oldest states in Central Asia. The first city of the Kesh oasis, after the military campaigns of Alexander the Macedonian, by the 3rd century BC, was in crisis due to various political and economic reasons, and the city and Podayotoqtepa, where it was located, became a ruin. The inhabitants of the city moved from the banks of the Shorabsay to the banks of the Oksuv river, to the territory of the present city of Kitab, and a new city was founded in this place. According to N.I. Krashennikova, a scientist who studied Kitab-Kesh archaeologically, Kesh, which was formed on the site of Kitab, was a large craft center in the 2nd century BC, the city area covered more than 40 hectares, and a fortress was built for defense. Inside the castle there was a craftsman's quarter with many luxurious buildings and attractive houses.

The second stage completely occupied the left side of the master. Also in the center of the scene is a deity, sitting on a carpet high up. One leg is bent at the knee and the other is hanging down. His right hand is on his waist and holds the lower part of the staff, the other hand is raised at shoulder height and is giving a command or gesture. There are figures of musicians around. They wore long clothes. One is playing the angular harp, which was popular until the 16th century. The body of the second musician is not clear, but he has an oud in his hand. Below the goddess are two sheep, looking at each other. In front of the sheep, flowers are opened and there is some kind of dish in between. The image of Srosh weighing the soul of a dead body, which is depicted on the threshold of the State Museum of the History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan, is the goddess of Rashn. The image of a horse in the scene is not accidental. The white horse Mihra is an incarnation of Mithra. In some cases, the horse is also interpreted as "carrying the dead body in the other world". According to Arrian, the crown prince of Cyrus, Cambyses, sacrificed a sheep to his father's grave every day, and a horse every month, and considered the horse to be a "sacrifice dedicated to the sun". Sometimes masters are represented in the form of various animals or horses. K. A. Inostrantsev wrote about the preservation of these traditions, drawing Persian burial customs and writing that "these customs are typical of the Gujarati style in the Arta-Virat book." In the paintings dedicated to his funeral, a man or a priest is not leading the horse, but is walking in front of it.

Another picture of a funeral shows two people carrying a flag and a saddled horse behind them.

So, the saddled horse in the image is dedicated to the goddess Mikhr as a sacrifice for the soul of the corpse, and the person performing the ritual - Srosh, is depicted as acting as an intermediary between the corpse and the goddesses, in some sources Srosh is represented as the "protector of souls". A stone in the An Juan cemetery in northern China depicts Srosh as a priest "consecrating food."

Guzor was one of the villages of the Kesh region in ancient and early medieval times, and it appears in the sources under the name of Khuzor. According to the researcher E.V. Rtveladze, the city of Guzor was built by Afrasiab in legends, and in fact, the oldest archaeological monuments in Guzor belong to the 1st century AD [13. b. 50-51]. Guzor was one of the villages located on the Silk Road from Tokhoristan to Sugdiya. Researchers consider the territory of Guzor as the border between the herdsman and the farming population. According to written sources, in the first half of the 8th century, the ruler of Guzor was a person named Sabukra. After the Arab conquerors failed to conquer Guzor by force, there is a record of a peace treaty with Sabukra and its inhabitants. These events may have taken place in the area of the Mardtepa archaeological monument, located in the south of Guzor, because the Mardtepa monument is located on the border with Tokharistan, and in the archaeological excavations it was found that its period lasted from the 1st century BC to the 7th century AD [14, p. 1148]. Sh. Kamoliddinov considers Sabukra, who ruled Guzor at the beginning of the 8th century, as one of the Turkish rulers, and in his opinion, Mardtepa archeological monument may have been Sabukra's residence. As-Samoni, who lived in the 12th century, gives information about the address of Surkhakat in Guzar village. If its content is translated from the Sugdian language, it can be translated as "Red City". Sh. Kamoliddinov believes that this address existed instead of the city of Guzor [15. s. 109-127]. From 1985-1986, A.A.Raimkulov and M.H.Isomiddinov from the scientific staff of the Institute of Archeology of the Russian Federation joined the research work at the early medieval Tortkoltepa monument located in the valley of the Turnasoy river, which is part of the historical geographical area of Kesh [16, p. Volume 5, Part 1]. The Shahrizabz district inspectorate of the Ministry of Culture and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the protection and scientific production of cultural heritage objects, the Institute of Archeology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Museum of Material and Cultural History named

after Shahrisabz city Amir Temur in cooperation to "Compile the catalog of archaeological monuments of the Kashkadarya region" In 2012, about 200 archaeological monuments in Yakkabog district of Kashkadarya region, and in 2013 in Shahrisabz district, were fully considered.

In conclusion, it can be said that the full-blooded archaeological study of the history and culture of the ancient Kesh region, the irrigation system, historical toponymy and historical geography, and the location of monuments began in the 40-50s of the last century. it became possible to make many clarifications in its geography. In particular, scientific research is ongoing on the issues of the location of ancient and early medieval monuments, the migration of cities, and the localization of medieval villages.

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